

Impact of replacing Na^+ with Ag^+ on the optical and spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} -doped tellurite glasses

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ABSTRACT

Er^{3+} doped tellurite glasses have attracted significant interest due to their broad emission band at 1.5 μm , the telecommunication window. Among them, the glasses in the $\text{TeO}_2\text{-ZnO-Na}_2\text{O}$ system are particularly suitable for waveguide fabrication using ion exchange. This study investigates the impact of substituting Na_2O with Ag_2O in the tellurite glass doped with Er^{3+} ions on its optical and spectroscopic properties, as well as its chemical durability when immersed in $\text{AgNO}_3\text{-KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$ molten salt baths, usually used for $\text{Ag}^+\text{-Na}^+$ exchange. The replacement of Na_2O with Ag_2O leads to an increase in thermal stability and refractive index due to the depolymerization of the glass network. When immersed in Ag -containing salt baths, the glass surface reacts with the molten salt bath, the reaction of which depends on the glass and molten salt bath composition. Diffusion of Ag^+ and preferential etching of TeO_2 can be obtained, as well as surface crystallization. The glass with the composition 80 TeO_2 – 10 ZnO – 10 Na_2O (in mol%) was found to be the most stable in the molten salt bath probably due to its polymerized network and so the most suitable glass for ion exchange processes and waveguide fabrication.

1. Introduction

Various glasses have been explored for waveguide fabrication, such as silicate [1], chalcogenide [2] and tellurite-based glasses [3], just to cite a few. Among these, tellurite glasses have attracted attention following the development of the first single-mode Nd^{3+} -doped tellurite fiber laser in 1994 [4] and the broadband Er^{3+} -doped tellurite fiber amplifier in 1997 [5]. Their characteristics, such as excellent glass-forming ability, good thermal and chemical stability, low phonon energy (within the range of 650–800 cm^{-1} , depending on their exact composition) and high linear and nonlinear refractive indices [6] make them promising hosts for photonic applications.

Compared to silica and silicate glasses, tellurite glasses have lower melting temperatures and a higher solubility for rare-earth (RE) ions, enabling efficient doping without luminescence concentration quenching [7]. When doped with RE ions, particularly with Er^{3+} ions, tellurite glasses emit broad emission band with high emission cross-sections, making them ideal candidates especially as integrated optical amplifiers widely applied in various fields, including telecommunications, sensing, and biophotonics [8]. These glass-based optical components enable the development of miniaturized photonic circuits, waveguides,

and optical interconnects, which are essential for high-speed data transmission and advanced optical processing [9]. Additionally, they can be used in medical imaging, environmental monitoring, and precision measurement systems, benefiting from their stability and adaptability in different operational environments [10,11]. Glass for integrated optics have been fabricated using different technologies such as femtosecond laser direct writing (fs-DLW) [12], UV direct printing [13], photolithography [14] and ion exchange [15] for example. Among these approaches, ion exchange has been established as a highly effective technique for the fabrication of active optical devices. This process involves replacing ions with other ions from a molten salt bath. It offers high optical gain per unit length, the versatility to accommodate multiple functions and compatibility with cost-effective mass production [16,17]. The $\text{Ag}^+\text{-Na}^+$ ion-exchange process is well-known and the replacement of Na^+ with Ag^+ is usually used to modify the optical properties of glass at its surface. Sakida *et al.* reported the successful fabrication of planar waveguides in tellurite glass using $\text{Ag}^+\text{-Na}^+$ ion-exchange [18]. Ag^+ can also be used to enhance the optical performance as demonstrated from Er^{3+} -doped tellurite glass waveguides fabricated using $\text{Ag}^+\text{-Na}^+$ ion exchange [19]. However, the chemical durability of tellurite glasses remains a challenge during exchange

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process as this process involves immersing the glass in salt baths. In a typical ion exchange experiment, the process is performed by immersing the glass in a molten nitrate salt bath for several hours which can lead to partial dissolution of the glass [20]. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the impact of the glass batch and salt compositions on the chemical durability of the glass during the process is essential for optimizing the ion exchange process and so the performance of optical waveguide.

This study aims to investigate the effects of replacing Na₂O with Ag₂O on the optical and spectroscopic properties of tellurite glass, providing insights into how a complete substitution of Na with Ag during the ion exchange process can potentially influence the material's characteristics. Additionally, the chemical durability of the glasses in a molten salt bath is examined to determine the optimal composition of the glass and of the molten salt bath for Na-to-Ag exchange while minimizing glass etching.

2. Experimental

Glasses with the compositions $x\text{TeO}_2 - (90-x)\text{ZnO} - (10-y)\text{Na}_2\text{O} - y\text{Ag}_2\text{O} - 2.5\text{Er}_2\text{O}_3$ with $x = 70; 75$ and 80 and $y = 0$ and 10 (in mol%) were synthesized using standard melting process. The glasses were labeled as $x\text{Na}$ ($y = 0$) and $x\text{Ag}$ ($y = 10$), respectively. The batches were prepared using the following raw materials: TeO₂ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), ZnO (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), Na₂CO₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), Er₂O₃ (SigmaAldrich, 99.99%) and Ag₂SO₄ (Honeywell, 99.5%). The 10 g batches were melted in quartz crucible for 10 min at 775 °C in air atmosphere. After melting the glasses were quenched onto a brass plate and then annealed in a muffle furnace at ~40 °C below the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the glasses for 3 h to release the internal stress. The glasses were cut and polished for spectroscopic measurements.

The density was measured using the Archimedes method. Ethanol was used as the immersion liquid and the accuracy of the results is ± 0.02 g/cm³.

The glass transition temperature (T_g), onset of crystallization (T_x) and crystallization temperatures (T_p) were measured using differential thermal analysis (DTA, Netzsch Jupiter F1 instrument). The T_g was taken at the inflection point of the endothermic peak, whereas T_x and T_p were taken at the onset and maximum of the exothermic peak, respectively. The thermal stability of the glasses against crystallization was evaluated using the temperature difference between the glass transition and onset of crystallization temperatures, defined as $\Delta T = T_x - T_g$. All measurements were conducted with an accuracy ± 3 °C.

The Raman spectra were acquired using Renishaw inVia Qontor Raman microscope equipped with a cooled charge-coupled device (CCD) camera and a 532 nm laser for excitation. Measurements were performed on undoped glasses to avoid luminescence bands of Er³⁺ ion.

The refractive indices were obtained at 443, 633, 825, 1061, 1312 and 1533 nm using the prism coupling technique using the Abbe refractometer (Model 2010/M, Metricon) achieving an accuracy of ± 0.001 .

The absorption spectra were measured using UV-VIS-Near-IR spectrophotometer (UV-3600 Plus, Shimadzu) on polished samples within the wavelength range of 340–600 nm and a step size of 1 nm. The absorption cross-sections, $\sigma_{\text{abs}}(\lambda)$, were determined from absorbance using Eq. (1):

$$\sigma_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) = \frac{\ln 10 D(\lambda)}{NL} \quad (1)$$

where $D(\lambda)$ is the absorbance, N is the concentration of Er³⁺ ions in the glass (ions/cm³), L is the thickness of the sample. The accuracy of absorption cross-section is ± 10 %.

The IR absorption spectra were measured in transmission mode using the FTIR2000 PerkinElmer spectrometer with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and

an accumulation of 8 scans.

The spectroscopic properties of the glasses were examined at room temperature, with the samples ground into powder to allow a comparison of their emission intensity. A continuous-wave 980 nm monochromatic single-mode fiber-pigtailed laser diode (CM962UF76P-10R, Oclaro) was used for excitation. The upconversion and NIR emission spectra were acquired using a Spectro 320–131 optical spectrum analyzer (Instrument Systems Optische Messtechnik GmbH, Germany). The emission spectra associated with the Ag spectroscopic properties were measured using Edinburgh FLS1000 photoluminescence spectrometer using a xenon lamp as an excitation source.

The XRD patterns were measured using the X-ray diffractometer (XRD) analyzer (PANalytical Empyrean) with Cu K α X-ray radiation ($\lambda = 0.15405$ nm) in the 2θ range from 10 to 70 °C with a step size of 0.05 °C.

Carl Zeiss Crossbeam 540 Gemini SEM with an Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (X-MaxN 80) detector (EDS) was used to analyze the surface of the glasses coated with a conductive carbon layer. The composition of the glasses was quantified using an Electron Probe MicroAnalyzer (EPMA) coupled with a wavelength dispersive X-ray analyzer (WDX). The accuracy is ± 0.1 at%.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the density and thermal properties of the investigated glasses. The density, glass transition, and crystallization temperatures were found to be comparable to those values of the similar glasses reported by Lumiere *et al.* [21] and Massera *et al.* [22]. As expected, the Ag₂O containing glasses have higher density than the Na₂O containing glasses because of the higher molar mass of Ag₂O ($M_{\text{Ag}_2\text{O}} = 231.735$ g/mol) compared to that of Na₂O ($M_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} = 61.9789$ g/mol). The increase in TeO₂ content from 70 to 80 mol% results also in an increase in the density. This is due to higher molar mass of TeO₂ ($M_{\text{TeO}_2} = 159.6$ g/mol) that is replacing ZnO ($M_{\text{ZnO}} = 81.38$ g/mol).

The changes in the glass composition have also a noticeable impact on the thermal properties of the glass. The Ag glasses show lower T_g and higher T_x than the Na glasses, and consequently, higher ΔT , suggesting that the replacement of Na₂O by Ag₂O can be used to increase the resistance of the glass toward crystallization [23]. As seen in Fig. 1a, the shape of the crystallization peaks is sharper and well defined in the Ag glasses than in Na glasses suggesting that the change in the glass composition has an impact on the nucleation and growth properties [24]. An increase in the TeO₂ content leads to a decrease in T_g , T_x , T_p as well as in ΔT . The decrease in T_g can be related to changes in the glass structure as evidenced in Fig. 1b. The Raman spectra are normalized to the band at 664 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to the stretching modes of TeO₄ units. The Raman spectra also depict a band at 745 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the symmetrical stretching of Te–O and Te=O bonds that contain non-bridging oxygens (NBOs) in TeO₃ and TeO₃₊₁ units [21]. The full attribution of Raman bands can be found in [21]. The changes in the glass composition lead to slight changes in the Raman spectra; the band at 745 cm⁻¹ increases in intensity compared to the band at 660 cm⁻¹ when x and y decreases and increases, respectively. These changes suggest the progressive depolymerization of the tellurite network associated with an increase in the distorted TeO₃/TeO₃₊₁ units at the

Table 1
Thermal properties and the density of the investigated glasses.

Sample	ρ (g/cm ³) ± 0.02 g/ cm ³	T_g (± 3 °C)	T_x (± 3 °C)	T_p (± 3 °C)	$\Delta T = T_x - T_g$ (°C) ± 6 °C
70Na	5.25	318	381	455	63
70Ag	5.63	308	416	432	108
75Na	5.28	314	361	388	47
75Ag	5.65	305	412	425	107
80Na	5.31	312	342	364	30
80Ag	5.66	304	397	416	93

Fig. 1. Thermograms (a) and normalized Raman spectra (b) of the investigated Na and Ag glasses. Thin and thick lines are for the Na and Ag glasses, respectively.

Fig. 2. Refractive indices (a), IR (b) and absorption spectra (c) of the investigated glasses. Thin and thick lines are for the Na and Ag glasses, respectively.

expense of TeO₄ units when Na₂O is replaced by Ag₂O and when the concentration of TeO₂ decreases. The increase in the depolymerization of the tellurite glass network is confirmed by the decrease in T_g seen in Table 1 [25]. It is interesting to point out that the network is more depolymerized when Na₂O is replaced by Ag₂O in the low TeO₂ concentrated glass. Here, the 70Ag and 80Na glasses are suspected to have the most depolymerized and the most polymerized network compared to the other glasses, respectively.

The refractive index dispersion of the glasses is presented in Fig. 2a. The increase in x leads to a rise in the refractive index in agreement with [26]. The refractive index also increases when replacing Na₂O by Ag₂O due to the increased average electronic polarizability of glass network [27]. The overall polarizability contribution is determined by the polarizability of the individual ions in the glass ($\alpha_{Na^+} = 0.18 \text{ \AA}^3$ [24], $\alpha_{Ag^+} = 1.7\text{--}2.2 \text{ \AA}^3$ [28]).

The IR spectra of the investigated glasses (Fig. 2b) exhibit broad absorption bands associated with hydroxyl (OH) groups. The bands at $\sim 2350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to the presence of “very strongly” hydrogen bonded OH⁻ groups and of free, weakly associated hydroxyl groups, respectively, according to Feng *et al.* [29]. A distinct increase in intensity of the band at $\sim 2350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed when replacing Na₂O by Ag₂O. This band may also arise from the anharmonic contribution of the bending mode at $2\delta_{OH}$ [30].

Fig. 2c depicts the absorption spectrum of the glasses which show the characteristic absorption bands of Er³⁺ ions. These bands correspond to the 4f-4f electronic transitions of Er³⁺ from the ground state $^4I_{15/2}$ to the different excited states. The optical bandgap position shifts to higher wavelengths when x and y increase in agreement with the changes in the refractive index (Fig. 2a) and in the Raman spectra (Fig. 1b). One should point out that the changes in the glass composition have no impact on the shape and position of the absorption bands centered at 980 and 1530 nm (not shown here) nor on their corresponding absorption coefficient and absorption cross-sections (Table 2). One should mention that the absorption cross-sections are in agreement with those previously reported for tellurite glasses [21,31,32].

Fig. 3a presents the NIR emission spectra of the investigated glasses obtained under 980 nm excitation. The observed emission band corresponds to the transition $^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ of Er³⁺ ions and is typical for Er³⁺ ions located in amorphous network. The intensity of this emission band remains unchanged within the accuracy of the measurement when changing the glass composition suggesting that the sites of Er³⁺ ions are similar in all glasses. Fig. 3b represents the upconversion spectra of the glasses (excitation at 980 nm). The spectra show distinct emission bands around 525, 549, and 660 nm, corresponding to the 4f transitions $^2H_{11/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$, $^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$, and $^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ of Er³⁺ ions, respectively [33, 34]. The similarity in shape of these emission bands among all the investigated glasses confirm that the local surroundings of Er³⁺ ions is similar in all samples. One can notice that an increase in y almost suppresses the upconversion properties of the glasses. As the glasses exhibit similar absorption cross-sections at 980 nm, the incorporation of Ag₂O is thought to influence the Er³⁺ ions solubility in the glasses by modifying the connectivity of the glass network. The depolymerization of the tellurite network induced by the replacement of the Na₂O by Ag₂O is

Table 2
Optical properties of the investigated glasses.

Glass	$N_{Er^{3+}}$ (10 ²⁰)/ ions/cm ³ ±5 %	α_{abs} (cm ⁻¹) @980 nm	σ_{abs} @980 nm (10 ⁻²¹)/ cm ² ±10 %	α_{abs} (cm ⁻¹) @1530 nm	σ_{abs} @1530 nm (10 ⁻²¹)/ cm ² ±10 %
70Na	11.26	2.90	2.57	9.02	8.02
70Ag	10.80	3.03	2.80	8.28	7.67
75Na	11.02	2.79	2.53	8.97	8.13
75Ag	10.58	2.31	2.18	7.56	7.15
80Na	10.80	3.01	2.78	8.33	7.72
80Ag	10.35	2.59	2.51	7.89	7.62

suspected to increase the distance between the Er³⁺ ions, leading to decrease in green and red UC emission intensities as suggested in [21].

The glasses were immersed in molten salt bath with the composition $z\text{AgNO}_3 - 40\text{KNO}_3 - (60-z)\text{NaNO}_3$, where $z = 1, 5$ and 15 (in mol%) for 1 h at 10 °C below the T_g of the glass. These conditions are similar to those used for ion exchange between the Na⁺ ions in the glass and the Ag⁺ ions from the molten salt bath [19,35]. As shown in Fig. 4, the immersion of the glasses in molten salt bath has a strong impact on the shape and intensity of the emission centered at 1.5 μm. The shape of the emission band changes significantly, especially when the glasses are immersed in the highly AgNO₃ concentrated molten salt bath ($z = 15$) suggesting changes in the sites of Er³⁺ ions occurring during the glass immersion in the molten salt bath. The change in the shape of the emission band suggests the incorporation of Er³⁺ ions into a crystalline phase during the immersion treatment. An enhancement in intensity of the emission is observed from the glasses immersed in the molten salt bath with $z = 1$. This enhancement in the spectroscopic properties of the glasses after immersion treatment suggests that some Ag⁺ ions from the molten salt bath enter in the glass network, known to enhance the Er³⁺ spectroscopic properties [19]. One can notice that the increase in intensity of the emission correlates with, and follows, the rise in TeO₂ content. However, a significant decrease in the intensity of emission is observed after immersing the glasses in a molten salt bath with high concentration of AgNO₃ ($z = 15$). One should point out that the decrease is less apparent for the highly TeO₂ concentrated glass ($x = 80$).

Similar changes in the upconversion spectra were observed as shown in Fig. 5. Sharp peaks can be seen after immersing the glasses in the molten salt with $z = 15$ and the intensity of the green and red emission decreases after immersion. The changes in local environment around Er³⁺ ions after the immersion in the molten salt baths are also confirmed by the change in the green to red intensity corresponding to the hypersensitive transition $^2H_{11/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ and $^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$, respectively [36]. As for Fig. 4, the changes in the upconversion properties are less pronounced as the concentration of TeO₂ increases indicating that the glass with the most depolymerized network is the most sensitive to the immersion in the molten salt bath.

The XRD spectra of the glasses were measured after immersion. As shown in Fig. 6, sharp peaks can be seen in the XRD pattern after immersion, especially after immersion in the molten salt bath with $z = 15$. Some of the identified peaks correspond to the NaNO₃ (ICDD 01-089-2828), KNO₃ (ICDD 00-034-0379), and AgNO₃ (ICDD 04-011-0014) crystalline phases, which can be attributed to the presence of the molten salt solution solidified at the surface of the glasses. Additional peaks can be seen confirming the growth of crystals in the glasses during the immersion in molten salt bath. These crystals could be related Zn₂Te₃O₈ (ICSD: 00-036-0888), Er₂Te₅O₁₃ (ICSD: 00-051-0285) and/or Na₂Te₄O₉ (ICSD: 00-051-0441) crystals as similar crystals were reported to grow during a thermal treatment in glasses in similar glass system [21]. In agreement with the spectroscopic properties of the glasses after immersion, less peaks are seen in the highly TeO₂ concentrated glass ($x = 80$).

The composition of the glasses after immersion was analyzed. The SEM image and composition analysis line scans were taken from the cross-section of the glasses and are shown in Fig. 7. The surface of the glasses changes dramatically after immersion, especially when increasing the amount of AgNO₃ at the expense of NaNO₃ in the molten salt. At low concentration of AgNO₃ ($z = 1$), the surface of the glasses, independently of their composition, remains flat but a lower concentration of TeO₂ and higher concentration of Na₂O were detected suggesting a preferential etching of TeO₂ during the immersion process. No Ag was detected at the surface of the glasses. Increasing the AgNO₃ content in the bath to $z = 5$ enhances the etching process of the glass while promoting, at the same time, the Ag⁺-Na⁺ ion exchange, as indicated by a decrease in the Na₂O concentration and the corresponding increase in Ag₂O content from the surface. Bubbles due to glass etching can be seen mainly in the glass with $x = 70$ suggesting that a

Fig. 3. NIR (a) and UC (b) spectra of the investigated glasses ($\lambda_{exc} = 980$ nm). Thin and thick lines are for the Na and Ag glasses, respectively.

Fig. 4. Emission spectra of the Na glasses with $x = 70$ (a), $x = 75$ (b), $x = 80$ (c) before and after immersing into molten salt baths with different AgNO_3 content (z). The spectra were normalized relative to the band with the highest intensity to ensure a consistent basis for comparison. Insets show the relative intensity of the emission at 1533 nm as a function of z . All spectra were obtained under 980 nm excitation.

Fig. 5. Upconversion spectra of the Na glasses with $x = 70$ (a), $x = 75$ (b), $x = 80$ (c) before and after immersing into molten salt baths with different AgNO_3 content (z). The spectra were normalized relative to the band 668 nm. Insets show the relative intensity of the emission at 668 nm as a function of z . All spectra were obtained under 980 nm excitation.

higher TeO_2 content can be used to increase the chemical stability of the glass in the molten salt as a result probably of more polymerized glass network as discussed in the previous section. When using a molten salt bath with a higher AgNO_3 concentrations ($z = 15$), the surface of the glasses is clearly deteriorated. Surface etching becomes more apparent, as evidenced by the low TeO_2 and ZnO content at the surface of the sample. A large amount Ag_2O can be also found on the surface of the glasses extending into the volume to a depth of $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$. One should point out that K was not detected in all the glasses after immersion.

Finally, a higher Er_2O_3 content is suspected at the surface of the glass after immersion which is confirmed from the elemental mapping as presented in Fig. 8, taken the glass with $x = 80$ immersed in the solution with $z = 15$ as an example. We confirm the formation of a surface rich in Ag and Er and low in Te and Na. It is clear from the SEM images that this immersion process results in porous surface which contains bubbles. Based on the XRD pattern and the emission spectra of the glasses after immersion, this layer is suspected to be also crystallized. The elemental distribution of Er suggests high concentration of Er^{3+} ions within this region, which explains the change in the shape of the emission and upconversion spectra.

4. Conclusions

In this study, Er^{3+} doped tellurite glasses were prepared in the TeO_2 - ZnO - Na_2O and TeO_2 - ZnO - Ag_2O glass systems using standard melting process in order to understand how the glass' characteristics can be influenced if complete substitution of Na with Ag is achieved during ion exchange process. The substitution Na_2O with Ag_2O can be used to increase the thermal stability of the glass. However, this change in the glass composition depolymerizes the glass network, increasing the refractive index, and decreasing the upconversion properties. Increasing the TeO_2 content from 70 to 80 mol% leads to a more polymerized glass network with higher refractive index and slightly lower upconversion properties.

The chemical durability of the glass in the TeO_2 - ZnO - Na_2O system when immersed in AgNO_3 - KNO_3 - NaNO_3 was investigated in order to determine the optimal composition of the glass and of the molten salts for Na-to-Ag exchange while minimizing glass etching. Glass etching with the formation of a porous and crystallized layer is expected to occur when the glasses are immersed in highly AgNO_3 concentrated molten salt bath. The elemental distribution of Er suggests high concentration of Er^{3+} ions within this modified region, in agreement with the changes in the shape of the emission bands measured at $1.5 \mu\text{m}$. A slight

Fig. 6. XRD pattern of the Na glasses with $x = 70$ (a), $x = 75$ (b), $x = 80$ (c) before and after immersing into molten salt bath. Also shown are the standard XRD patterns crystals of the $NaNO_3$ (ICDD 01-089-2828, 04-015-8750), KNO_3 (ICDD 00-034-0379), $AgNO_3$ (ICDD 04-011-0014), $Zn_2Te_3O_8$ (ICSD: 00-036-0888), $Na_2Te_4O_9$ (ICSD: 00-051-0441), and $Er_2(TeO_3)_3$ (ICSD: 00-051-0285).

enhancement in intensity of the emission centered at $1.5 \mu m$ under 980 nm excitation can be obtained by immersing the glasses in a molten salt bath with the $1AgNO_3-40KNO_3-59 NaNO_3$ (in mol%) due to the diffusion of Ag^+ in the glass as evidenced using SEM. It was found that the glass with the highest TeO_2 content is the most stable in the molten salt bath and so is a good candidate for ion exchange process.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Iuliia Kraskowski: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Khaldoun Nasser:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Chloe Hanneke:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Laeticia Petit:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation,

Fig. 7. SEM image and composition analysis of the investigated glasses with $x = 70, 75$ and 80 immersed in the molten salt bath with $z = 1, 5$ and 15 .

Fig. 8. SEM image and mapping of the elements of the glass with $x = 80$ after immersing into the molten salt bath with $z = 15$.

Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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